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Air pollution in the urban built environment: A comprehensive evaluation

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses air pollution levels in the city of Chania, Greece, utilizing a combination of bike-mounted sensors and stationary monitoring stations to analyze the spatial and temporal variability of microclimate conditions and key pollutants, including PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, CO, and NO₂. The data analysis reveals significant seasonal variations in air pollution levels, with concentrations peaking during winter, primarily due to increased emissions from heating-related combustion and reduced atmospheric dispersion. In contrast, summer months exhibit lower pollution levels, as favorable meteorological conditions enhance pollutant dispersion. In spring, periodic dust episodes contribute to elevated PM concentrations, further influencing seasonal air quality patterns. Weekday pollution levels are generally higher than those on weekends, primarily due to traffic emissions and daily commuting patterns. However, in spring and summer, this trend becomes less consistent, as increased leisure activities and tourism-related transport led to elevated pollutant concentrations on certain weekends. Spatially, the highest pollution concentrations are observed in the city center, where dense traffic and urban structures contribute to pollutant accumulation. Conversely, coastal areas record lower pollution levels, benefiting from natural ventilation and reduced vehicular activity. These findings underscore the need for integrated air quality assessments in urban planning and policy development. Strengthening public transportation networks, enforcing emission control measures, expanding urban green infrastructure, and enhancing real-time air quality monitoring are recommended strategies to mitigate air pollution. By implementing these measures, cities can enhance air quality, public health, and environmental resilience, fostering more sustainable and equitable urban development.

1. Introduction

Air pollution has become a critical global challenge, driven by rapid urbanization, industrialization, and development activities (Zhang et al., 2016). It refers to the presence of harmful substances, such as chemical, particulate, or radiation, in the atmosphere at concentrations, durations, or quantities exceeding natural levels. These pollutants can potentially negatively impact human health, ecosystems, and materials, both in the short and long term (Boogaard et al., 2024; Wickham et al., 2019). Air pollution includes any natural or human made chemical compounds, whether in gaseous, liquid, or solid form, that enter the atmosphere in amounts that pose a risk to living organisms and the environment. (European Court of Auditors, 2018).

The degradation of air quality has been exacerbated by unplanned and unregulated urban growth, excessive fossil fuel consumption, and inadequate national and international legislation. Over 90 % of air pollution-related deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries

(Gurjar et al., 2016). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), air pollution is responsible for an estimated seven million premature deaths annually, due to cardiovascular diseases, stroke, pneumonia, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and cancer (Gurjar et al., 2008; Li et al., 2020). Furthermore, studies highlight the severe health implications of air pollution, with (Katsouyanni et al., 1997) reporting a clear link between particulate matter exposure and increased pneumonia incidence in children. It is estimated that nine out of ten individuals worldwide breathe air with pollutant levels exceeding WHO guidelines that identifies particulate matter (PM), ozone (O₃), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) as the most harmful air pollutants to human health (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2021). It is a fact that in the European Union, data from the European Environment Agency (EEA) attributes approximately 400,000, 75,000, and 13,600 premature deaths to PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃ exposure, respectively (Papamitsou et al., 2020). The "polluter pays" principle forms the foundation of the European Union's environmental strategy, with the

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prevention and remediation of environmental damage as key guiding principles. Since the mid-1970s, the EU has implemented environmental action programs that establish frameworks and objectives for future actions across all sectors of environmental policy. In 2018, an estimated 96 % of EU urban residents were exposed to air pollutant levels deemed harmful by the WHO (European Environment Agency (EEA), 2018). Urban populations are particularly vulnerable to air pollution due to the high concentration of emissions from sources such as road transport and the limited pollutant dispersion in cities compared to rural areas (European Environment Agency, 2018).

A substantial amount of air quality monitoring data often fails to provide the scientific community, policymakers, regulators, and the public with a clear and easily interpretable picture of air quality conditions. To address this gap, environmental authorities have adopted the Air Quality Index (AQI) as a tool for data interpretation and communication, especially in light of the significant health risks posed by air pollution. The AQI, a composite multi-pollutant index, was developed to simplify the assessment of air quality by condensing complex data from various pollutants into a single metric. This metric allows for easier communication and public understanding of air quality and the associated health risks (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2021; Gurjar et al., 2008; Hime et al., 2018; Sadeghi et al., 2015). The AQI categorizes air quality into six classifications: Good, Satisfactory, Moderately Polluted, Poor, Very Poor, and Severe. Each category reflects the potential health impact of the prevailing pollutant levels. The AQI is calculated based on the concentrations of key pollutants, such as PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂, CO, O₃ (Odekanle et al., 2020). These pollutants are selected due to their widespread presence and significant impact on public health. Moreover, national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS) vary between countries, leading to differences in AQI thresholds and levels across nations. Despite these differences, the AQI remains a crucial tool for conveying air quality information to diverse stakeholders, providing an accessible means to assess and mitigate the risks of air pollution on a global scale.

Recent studies across Europe have extensively examined air pollution, focusing on its sources, concentrations, and health impacts on urban populations (Jaume et al., 2022; Sicard et al., 2021). European Union policies have successfully reduced certain pollutants, such as SO₂ and Pb, through stringent regulations and mitigation strategies. However, urban areas continue to grapple with elevated levels of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂, with disparities persisting across socioeconomic and geographic contexts. Lower-income and densely populated regions are disproportionately exposed to higher pollution levels, exacerbating public health risks. For instance, many European capitals exemplify these issues: London reports persistently high NO₂ concentrations driven by traffic, despite the implementation of the Ultra Low Emission Zone; Paris experiences recurrent PM spikes from vehicle emissions, prompting temporary traffic restrictions; and Madrid, while benefiting from regulatory measures and public awareness campaigns, continues to face elevated NO₂ and PM levels in high-traffic areas (Font et al., 2019; Salas et al., 2021). In Eastern Europe, Bucharest faces significant air quality challenges driven by industrial activities and vehicle emissions. In addition, meteorological factors, including temperature, wind patterns, humidity, and atmospheric stability, critically influence pollutant dispersion and accumulation, exacerbating air quality issues in urban settings. This interplay has garnered substantial research attention, particularly in emerging economies where rapid urbanization intensifies pollution concerns (Zhu et al., 2021).

The Mediterranean basin faces distinct air quality challenges due to the complex interplay of anthropogenic emissions, natural sources, marine influences, and Saharan dust intrusions, which complicate the analysis of PM dynamics (Chatoutsidou et al., 2025). In Greece, elevated levels of NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ are particularly pronounced in the Athens metropolitan area, where winter heating and meteorological conditions exacerbate pollution. While Athens faces severe air quality challenges, Ioannina records the poorest conditions in Greece, due to

extensive wood burning, while other cities such as Thessaloniki and Patras also experience elevated pollutant levels (Dimitriou and Mihailopoulos, 2024). A comparative analysis of air quality standards in Eastern Mediterranean countries revealed that national PM_{2.5} limits can exceed WHO guidelines by up to tenfold, highlighting the urgent need for stricter regulatory alignment to reduce disease burden and premature mortality (Faridi et al., 2023). Health impact studies further underscore this urgency, with (Psistaki et al., 2023) reporting that a 10 µg/m³ increase in PM_{2.5} is associated with a 1.10 % rise in cardiovascular mortality in Thessaloniki and a 3.07 % increase in mortality in Limassol on the same day. In Sicily, Italy, most PM₁₀ exceedances between 2013 and 2015 were attributed to Saharan dust intrusions, identified through three independent modeling approaches (Cuspilici et al., 2017). In Chania, Greece, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations generally remain below WHO limits but exhibit significant seasonal variability, driven by African dust, residential heating, and biomass burning, with mineral dust contributing over 30 % to PM levels, followed by sulfates, traffic, sea salt, and road dust (Chatoutsidou and Lazaridis, 2022). A multi-city study of Venice, Marseille, Thessaloniki, and Barcelona further revealed distinct seasonal patterns in fine particulate matter: winter peaks in Venice and Marseille, autumn maxima in Thessaloniki, and spring elevations in Barcelona, denoting the combined influence of meteorology and local emission sources on air quality across Mediterranean cities (Salameh et al., 2015).

Despite progress in air quality monitoring, stationary networks limit spatial resolution and fail to capture microenvironmental variations. To overcome these limitations, this study introduces a hybrid monitoring approach in Chania, Greece, combining fixed stations with mobile bicycle-mounted sensors. This method enables high-resolution mapping of pollution hotspots and one year analysis of pollutant dynamics, offering a scalable model for other mid-sized Mediterranean cities.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Case study

Chania city, located on the island of Crete and it is the largest Greek island and the fifth largest in the Mediterranean which serves as an ideal location for monitoring air pollution due to its unique socio-economic and environmental conditions (Fig. 1). This Mediterranean city enjoys a subtropical climate characterized by sunny, dry summers and mild, rainy winters, with its coastal location influencing temperature patterns compared to other Greek cities without coastal access (Kolokotsa et al., 2009; Tsekeri et al., 2025).

According to the latest census by (European Union, 2018; Population, 2023), is the second most populous city on Crete, with a total population of 155,443 across its seven municipalities, of which the municipality of Chania accounts for 110,646 residents. Demographically, Chania has a birth rate of 8.96 per 1000 inhabitants and a death rate of 8.55 per 1000 inhabitants. Rapid urbanization and increased tourism have led to heightened vehicular traffic, energy consumption, construction activities, and key sources of air pollution. Furthermore, Chania's historical architecture and narrow streets contribute to congestion and localized pollution, compounded by a lack of public transportation options. In addition, it has limited public open spaces, averaging just 2 m² per resident and a total green area of 0.28 km², equivalent to 5.26 m² per person (Dimelli, 2020). The city's unique socio-economic profile and its challenges related to urban sprawl and tourism pressure make it an exemplary case for comprehensive air quality monitoring using tools like AQI. Regular monitoring will also provide critical insights into the health impacts of air pollution (Chalvatzaki and Lazaridis, 2010), help identify specific pollution sources, and guide local policies on transportation, urban planning, and public health.

Fig. 1. Mediterranean Sea Map -Chania, Greece case study.

2.2. Data collection

This study employs a hybrid monitoring system integrating stationary sensor kits at Chania's bike-sharing stations with mobile sensors mounted on bicycles (Fig. 2): Specifically.

a) Stationary Monitoring System: Each of Chania's two bike-sharing stations is equipped with a custom sensor kit powered directly by the docking station. These kits measure SO_2 , NO_2 , CO , O_3 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , air temperature, relative humidity, and GPS coordinates (latitude and longitude) at 1-min intervals. Station 1 (S1) is situated in a parking area near the coastal side (Defkalionos Street), offering a distinct environment characterized by proximity to the sea and lower traffic congestion. In contrast, Station 2 (S2) is located in the city

center (Markopoulou Street), near the Old Chania Market, a densely populated and highly trafficked urban area with both vehicle and pedestrian activity. This site includes a small parking lot and tree cover, reflecting a high-exposure pollution setting.

b) Mobile Monitoring System: Twenty-eight bicycles are fitted with low-power sensor kits designed for mobile deployment. Each kit records $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , air temperature, relative humidity, and GPS coordinates. Data collection operates in two modes: (i) Docked Mode, where parked bicycles recorded hourly data, and (ii) Mobile Mode, where rented bicycles collected minute-by-minute data across the city.

All sensors communicated via Wi-Fi to a digital platform for real-time transmission, visualization, and secure storage. Although factory-

Fig. 2. (Left) S1 and S2 Bike station in the city, (Right) Bicycles in the bike stations equipped with sensors.

calibrated, all sensors underwent additional calibration against high-precision reference stations measuring the same pollutants over an extended period to ensure data reliability and comparability. A detailed description of the methodology that followed for assessing the air pollution in Chania city is provided in Section 2.3.

2.3. Methodology

The methodology outlined below (Fig. 3) uses geospatial and statistical tools to map pollutant distributions, identify hotspots, and assess the AQI. Specifically for the monitoring period December 2023–November 2024.

- **Data Management:** Data from stationery and mobile sensors are processed in MATLAB, where GPS coordinates (Longitude and Latitude) are converted to XY coordinates ensuring compatibility with geospatial analysis tools.
- **Spatial Statistics and Clustering:** Processed data are imported into ArcGIS, and Spatial Statistics tools are used to conduct grouping analysis. This mapping identifies pollution clusters based solely on air quality similarities, free from spatial or administrative constraints, ensuring clusters reflect zones with only consistent pollutant patterns.
- **Optimal Cluster Determination:** The optimal number of clusters is established using pseudo-F-statistic plots in ArcGIS, to assess cluster quality, where a higher pseudo-F value indicates more cohesive and well-separated clusters. This ensures that the final clustering structure is statistically robust.
- **Geographical Distribution Analysis:** The mean center of each cluster is computed in ArcGIS to map pollution hotspots across Chania’s urban zones.

- **Raster Interpolation:** Inverse Distance Weighting is applied to create heatmaps, interpolating continuous pollutants and highlight high-risk areas with elevated pollutant levels.
- **Seasonal Analysis:** Once the optimal clustering structure is established, results are analyzed across seasons to assess seasonal pollution across the year. The data are analyzed and presented according to seasonal variations, specifically categorized into Winter (December to February), Spring (March to May), Summer (June to August), and Autumn (September to November). This methodology has been effectively applied in various research studies (US Environmental Protection Agency, 2015).
- **AQI Calculation:** Using only the stationary sensor data, computations were based on daily mean concentrations of SO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}, the maximum hourly NO₂ concentration, and the maximum 8-h CO concentration. Breakpoints for these pollutants follow the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) scale. The AQI for each pollutant is derived using a standardized formula as presented in (eq. (1)):

$$AQI_i = \frac{AQI_{max} - AQI_{min}}{C_{imax} - C_{imin}} (C_p - C_{imin}) + AQI_{min} \text{ eq. (1)}$$

Where: AQ_i: The sub-index for pollutant i (where i = 1,2,N i = 1, 2, and N is the total number of pollutants).

C_p: The observed pollutant concentration measured by the sensors.

C_{imin}: The lower bound of the concentration range for pollutant i, as defined by regulatory standards.

C_{imax}: The upper bound of the concentration range for pollutant i, as defined by regulatory standards.

AQ_{Imin}:The AQI value corresponding to C_{imin}

AQ_{Imax}:The AQI value corresponding to C_{imax}

Table 1 is created based on key pollutants, which provides AQI values and corresponding pollutant concentration ranges. The maximum calculated sub-index is taken as the overall AQI, which is

Fig. 3. Methodology Flow chart.

Table 1

AQI limits are based on each pollutant.

AQI	AQI	PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³) (Mean daily)	PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³) (Mean daily)	NO ₂ (µg/m ³) (Mean hourly)	SO ₂ (µg/m ³) (Mean daily)	CO(µg/m ³) (Mean 8h)
Good	0–50	0<C _i < 12	0<C _i < 54	0<C _i < 53	0<C _i < 35	0<C _i < 4.4
Moderate	51–100	12.1<C _i < 35.4	55<C _i < 154	54<C _i < 100	36<C _i < 75	4.5<C _i < 9.4
Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups	101–150	35.5<C _i < 55.4	155<C _i < 254	101<C _i < 360	76<C _i < 185	9.5<C _i < 12.4
Unhealthy	151–200	55.5<C _i < 150.4	255<C _i < 354	361<C _i < 649	186<C _i < 304	12.5<C _i < 15.4
Very Unhealthy	201–300	150.5<C _i < 250.4	355<C _i < 424	650<C _i < 1249	305<C _i < 604	15.5<C _i < 30.4
Hazardous	301–500	250.5<C _i < 500.4	425<C _i < 604	1250<C _i < 2049	605<C _i < 1004	30.5<C _i < 50.4

classified on a scale of 0–500 into six quality categories: good (0–50), moderate (51–100), unhealthy for sensitive groups (101–150), unhealthy (151–200), very unhealthy (201–300), and hazardous (301–500).

3. Results

3.1. Bike stations

The comparative analysis of the S1 (Figure S1, Figure S2) and S2 (Figure S5, Figure S6) monitoring stations in Chania highlight distinct environmental dynamics driven by their unique geographical locations and seasonal variations. Specifically, S1, positioned in the coastal area, demonstrates greater variability in air temperature and relative humidity, influenced by natural factors such as sea breezes and lower urban activity levels. The temperature at S1 fluctuates significantly,

ranging from approximately 10 °C–35 °C, with higher humidity levels attributable to the moisture-laden environment near the sea. Seasonally, S1 exhibits a gradual temperature increase from winter to summer, peaking between June and August, followed by a decline in autumn. This seasonal trend aligns with typical coastal climatology, where the proximity to the sea moderates temperature extremes. Conversely, S2, located in the densely populated and heavily trafficked city center, exhibits more stable temperature patterns. S2 records higher temperature peaks during summer and milder lows during winter, a characteristic of urban environments where the built infrastructure retains heat and suppresses natural variability. Humidity levels at S2 are lower and more consistent, reflecting the dominance of anthropogenic influences over natural climatic factors.

An analysis of PM_{2.5} (Figure S3, Figure S7) and PM₁₀ (Figure S4, Figure S8) concentrations at the S1 and S2 monitoring stations reveal notable differences shaped by their urban contexts. At S1, located near

Fig. 4. Monthly variations in air pollutant index levels.

the coastal area with less traffic congestion, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels exhibit greater variability. Lower quartile values suggest cleaner air during periods of minimal human activity, while occasional spikes highlight localized pollution events. In contrast, S2, situated in the dense city centre, records consistently higher median PM levels. The more stable distribution at S2 suggests persistent urban pollution influenced by vehicle emissions and limited natural dispersion.

The seasonal air quality analysis at the S1 and S2 monitoring stations in Chania in Fig. 4 reveals distinct spatial and temporal variations influenced by the stations' unique environmental settings and anthropogenic factors. The European AQI, as defined by the EEA, provides a standardized framework for interpreting pollutant levels across categories ranging from "Good" (light green) to "Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups" (orange) and beyond. At S1, located in a coastal parking area, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations remain within moderate levels. Conversely, S2, situated in the city center, consistently exhibits elevated PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations, as well as NO₂ and SO₂ levels are notably higher at S2, reflecting the intensified impact of urban emissions during winter. Furthermore, seasonal temperature inversions and limited atmospheric dispersion exacerbate pollutant accumulation at S2, whereas S1 benefits from its coastal location and favorable meteorological conditions, maintaining relatively lower pollution levels. CO levels, however, remain negligible across both stations. It is also important to consider the composition of PM, as air pollution index levels shown in Fig. 4 are largely driven by PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. At S1, natural sources such as sea salt aerosol contribute substantially to variability, whereas at S2, anthropogenic emissions from traffic, residential heating, and construction activities dominate. Seasonal trends further highlight variations in air quality between the two stations. During the spring months, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels at S1 are moderate, primarily influenced by natural particulate sources such as sea salt and dust, while NO₂, SO₂, and CO concentrations remain low due to the limited presence of urban and industrial emissions. In contrast, S2 experiences significantly higher PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels, attributable to urban activities and increased vehicular emissions. The summer season sees meteorological conditions amplifying the divergence in air quality, with S2 exhibiting elevated PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels due to urban heat island effects, while S1 maintains stable pollutant levels. However, NO₂ concentrations at S1 increase during this period, likely due to emissions from the adjacent parking lot, where vehicles contribute to localized pollution. In autumn, atmospheric changes drive increases in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at both stations, although S2 remains more affected due to urban density and cooler temperatures trapping pollutants near the ground. NO₂ and SO₂ levels peak at S2 during this period, further highlighting the influence of anthropogenic activity. Despite these variations, CO levels remain negligible across all seasons.

It is also important to consider the composition of PM, as air pollution index levels shown in Fig. 4 are largely driven by PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. We believe that these contrasting source profiles are largely explained by the geographical setting of the two sites: S1, located near the coast, is more exposed to marine air masses and long-range transport events, while S2, situated in the dense urban core, is strongly influenced by traffic congestion, heating demand, and limited dispersion within narrow streets. Seasonal trends further highlight variations in air quality between the two stations. During the spring months, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels at S1 are moderate, primarily influenced by natural particulate sources such as sea salt and dust, while NO₂, SO₂, and CO concentrations remain low due to the limited presence of urban and industrial emissions. In contrast, S2 experiences significantly higher PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels, attributable to urban activities and increased vehicular emissions. The summer season sees meteorological conditions amplifying the divergence in air quality, with S2 exhibiting elevated PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels due to urban heat island effects, while S1 maintains stable pollutant levels. However, NO₂ concentrations at S1 increase during this period, likely due to emissions from the adjacent parking lot, where vehicles contribute to localized pollution. In autumn, atmospheric

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In parallel, Fig. 5 presents the monthly average AQI values, derived from PM_{2.5} concentrations, measured at both monitoring stations. Elevated AQI levels during the winter months (December, January, and February) are primarily attributed to increased emissions from residential heating and vehicular traffic, together with reduced atmospheric dispersion caused by temperature inversions. Based on the European AQI health categories, the AQI values during winter predominantly fall within the "Moderate" (51–100) range, which may pose potential health risks for sensitive groups, such as individuals with respiratory or cardiovascular conditions. In contrast, spring and early summer exhibit improved air quality, with AQI values generally falling within the "Good" (0–50) category due to enhanced atmospheric mixing and reduced emissions, making outdoor activities safer for the general population. However, during July and August, coinciding with Chania's peak tourist season, AQI levels increase noticeably. The influx of visitors significantly amplifies anthropogenic activities, particularly transportation, resulting in higher PM_{2.5} concentrations. In autumn, particularly in October, AQI levels rise again, likely due to resuspended particulates and cooler temperatures that limit pollutant dispersion. While autumn AQI levels primarily remain in the "Moderate" range, they approach levels that could pose risks to sensitive groups.

Given that the AQI is primarily driven by PM_{2.5} concentrations, followed by PM₁₀, a supplementary analysis is performed to investigate the 24-h variations in the mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ across each month from December 2023 to November 2024. Specifically, Fig. 6 presents a detailed analysis of the hourly variations in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ mass concentrations across weekdays and weekends from December 2023 to November 2024. A consistent distinction is evident between weekday and weekend pollutant levels, with weekdays showing higher concentrations due to increased commuting, industrial activity, and urban emissions. Peaks in PM concentrations typically occur during the morning (6–8 AM) and evening (4–8 PM), corresponding to rush hours and elevated vehicular activity. These patterns are more pronounced at S2, situated in the city center, where urban density and traffic emissions significantly contribute to elevated pollution levels. Conversely, weekends consistently exhibit lower pollutant levels, highlighting the reduction in human activities during these periods. At S1, located in a coastal area, pollutant levels are generally lower than at S2, benefiting from enhanced dispersion and reduced urban influence. In addition, wind direction also plays a key role in shaping air quality, as onshore flows from the sea typically carry cleaner air masses and further promote dispersion. In the present study, the absence of a busy transportation area reinforces this effect, since incoming marine air is less influenced by local emissions. During winter, weekday PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations are notably higher due to increased emissions from residential heating and reduced atmospheric dispersion caused by temperature inversions. However, December also saw three days (two weekdays and one weekend day) affected by dust transport episodes from the Sahara Desert. While PM₁₀ concentrations on these days did not exceed the legal limit of 45 µg/m³, the presence of dust transport contributed to elevated pollutant levels compared to days without such events, indicating its influence on overall air quality. Weekends during this season exhibit lower concentrations, though some peaks persist. In spring and summer, improved meteorological conditions lead to reduced overall pollution levels. However, in spring, certain weekends exhibit higher PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations, likely influenced by increased leisure activities and tourism-related transport. During the peak tourist season in July and August, an influx of visitors increases weekend PM concentrations, particularly at S2, due to increased transportation and urban activity. Autumn marks a resurgence in pollutant levels, particularly during

Fig. 5. Monthly air quality index variation across Chania.

weekdays, driven by cooler temperatures that limit dispersion and increased urban activities.

3.2. Bicycle data

To assess seasonal air pollution patterns in Chania, bicycles equipped with sensors were used to measure air quality during winter, spring, summer and autumn. Specifically, Fig. 7 illustrates seasonal variations in $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations across Chania city where ArcGIS was employed to map spatial variations, highlighting pollution hotspots and seasonal trends across the city. During summer, $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations were consistently low, with most areas registering below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, represented by dark green zones on the air quality maps. In contrast, winter recorded the highest pollution levels, particularly in the northern coastal areas and the city center, where concentrations frequently exceeded $55 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Spring and autumn presented intermediate pollution levels, with $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations generally below $15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in most areas. However, localized hotspots were observed, particularly in urban centers and industrial zones, where concentrations ranged from 20 to $40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Last, autumn displayed a transitional air quality pattern, bridging the extremes of winter and summer, with occasional yellow zones ($20\text{--}30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) indicating moderate pollution.

In addition, Fig. 8 illustrates seasonal variations in PM_{10} concentrations across Chania city for the summer, winter, autumn, and spring periods. PM_{10} levels were significantly higher in winter, with large areas having concentrations between 30 and $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (yellow zones) and reaching $50\text{--}100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (orange zones) in high-traffic and densely populated neighborhoods. In spring, PM_{10} concentrations decreased, with most areas falling within the $20\text{--}30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ range (light green), while urban centers and major roadways still showed pockets of $30\text{--}50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (yellow). By summer, PM_{10} levels were at their lowest, with most of the city below $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (dark green). In autumn, PM_{10} concentrations rose compared to summer but remained lower than winter, with much of the city in the $20\text{--}30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ range and localized urban hotspots reaching $30\text{--}50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Thus, autumn is the transitional season that marks the gradual shift from summer's clean air to winter's higher pollution levels.

Moreover, to identify spatial patterns and seasonal variations in environmental and mobility data, cluster analysis was applied. In Chania, where bicycle usage and related measurements fluctuate across seasons, clustering allowed the classification of urban zones with similar characteristics, providing insight into the relationship between air quality and mobility behavior.

The seasonal cluster analysis in Fig. 9 and Table 2 reveals notable variations in air pollution distribution. Specifically, during winter,

pollution levels peaked in the urban core (Cluster 4), with $PM_{2.5}$ reaching $30.27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and PM_{10} rising to $58.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In contrast, coastal areas (Cluster 1) exhibited comparatively lower concentrations, while suburban zones (Clusters 2 and 3) showed intermediate values. In spring, a new fifth cluster (Cluster 5) emerged due to the increased cycling activity. The urban core (Cluster 2) remained the most polluted, with $PM_{2.5}$ at $17.10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while suburban expansion areas (Cluster 5) showed elevated $PM_{2.5}$ ($14.27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and PM_{10} ($19.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). During summer, $PM_{2.5}$ ($19.26 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and PM_{10} ($37.70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) concentrations were highest in the urban core (Cluster 2), while coastal and suburban clusters (Clusters 1, 3, and 4) recorded lower levels. Last, autumn represented the transitional period, with $PM_{2.5}$ levels peaking at $17.56 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the transitional zone (Cluster 3), and concentrations across other clusters showing an increase compared to summer.

4. Discussion

The aim of this study is to assess the air pollution in Chania. Winter months recorded the highest AQI values, with $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} levels exceeding WHO limits, particularly in the city center. These findings are consistent with previous studies, showing that heating emissions and limited atmospheric dispersion contribute to elevated pollution during colder months (Borge et al., 2019; Datta, 2023; Feng et al., 2020; Nigam et al., 2015). In contrast, summer exhibited the lowest concentrations, with $PM_{2.5}$ often below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and PM_{10} under $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, where these improvements reflect enhanced atmospheric mixing, reduced heating-related emissions, and natural ventilation from sea-breeze circulation. Compared to many European cities, Chania's air quality remains relatively favorable. For example, Athens, Paris, and Madrid frequently record substantially higher annual PM and NO_2 levels (Dimitriou and Mihalopoulos, 2024; Papamitsou et al., 2020; Sicard et al., 2021). Despite the implementation of mitigation policies, London and Paris continue to struggle with elevated NO_2 and PM concentrations linked to heavy traffic (Sicard et al., 2021) while Athens frequently exceeds EU pollution thresholds in winter (EEA, 2019). By contrast, Chania's AQI generally falls within the "Good" to "Moderate" range, with exceedances largely confined to winter peaks and localized summer increases associated with tourism-related traffic.

In this study, weekday concentrations in Chania were generally higher than those on weekends, reflecting traffic-related and human activity, though this pattern was less pronounced during the summer tourist season (Lonati et al., 2006; Vandeninden et al., 2024). In particular, this result was further confirmed in Birmingham, where weekday $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations were reported to be 20 % higher than weekend levels, driven by traffic activity (Jones et al., 2010). The

Fig. 6. Hourly Variations in PM_{2,5} and PM₁₀ concentrations across Weekdays and Weekend.

Fig. 7. PM_{2.5} values across seasons.

Fig. 8. PM₁₀ values across seasons.

intra-urban differences between the city center and the coastal area similarly highlight how urban density and traffic exacerbate pollution exposure in central districts, while natural ventilation mitigates concentrations in coastal areas. Similar intra-urban variation was reported in Athens, where monitoring stations in dense traffic and industrial areas in Greece, such as Athens Centre and Piraeus consistently recorded

higher PM_{2.5} concentrations during morning rush hours compared to suburban areas (Pateraki et al., 2013). The observed seasonal contrasts in Chania are consistent with documented meteorological influences on air quality in Mediterranean cities. Winter peaks in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ coincide with temperature inversions and reduced atmospheric mixing, which favor pollutant accumulation (Borge et al., 2019; Feng et al.,

Fig. 9. Spatial clustering of air quality measurements (winter, spring, summer, autumn).

Table 2
Cluster Groups analysis per season.

Season	Cluster Groups	Air Temp (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)
Winter	1	14.33	69.27	12.14	31.97
	2	18.26	65.53	19.18	25.39
	3	21.88	41.94	16.16	24.34
	4	14.21	66.59	30.27	58.04
Spring	1	19.94	56.08	8.53	28.47
	2	24.04	49.57	17.10	29.05
	3	21.17	52.33	8.73	25.84
	4	18.59	48.89	13.74	18.67
	5	22.90	41.09	14.27	19.25
Summer	1	32.50	44.66	10.36	24.80
	2	36.47	64.44	19.26	37.70
	3	31.56	45.49	13.39	17.75
	4	29.42	57.36	11.66	28.49
Autumn	1	25.55	55.03	10.15	27.82
	2	21.55	59.42	8.76	25.13
	3	29.02	48.79	17.56	26.75
	4	24.05	55.46	13.16	28.02

2020). In addition, the seasonal contrasts observed in Chania mirror those documented in prior local studies where authors in (Chatoutsidou et al., 2023) reported the contribution of residential wood burning as a major contributor to high particulate matter concentrations during the colder months. In summer, enhanced sea-breeze circulation and stronger winds facilitate dispersion, while spring reductions in PM₁₀ are partly attributable to rainfall events that remove particles from the atmosphere (Chatoutsidou and Lazaridis, 2022; Zhu et al., 2021).

When compared with other Greek cities, Chania's annual averages remain lower, but its winter pollution burden is still substantial. Chania's winter PM_{2.5} peaks (~30 µg/m³) were 25–35 % lower than those reported in Thessaloniki (35–45 µg/m³) and nearly 40–50 % lower than Athens (40–55 µg/m³) (Dimitriou and Mihalopoulos, 2024). Ioannina, however, consistently reports the highest winter PM_{2.5} levels in Greece, due to residential biomass burning and topographic constraints. Winter

mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in Ioannina reached ~57 µg/m³, nearly double those observed in Chania. Even in spring, Ioannina's average (~13.4 µg/m³) remained higher than many of Chania's summer values (<10 µg/m³) (Kakouri et al., 2025; Soupiadou et al., 2023; Stavroulas et al., 2020). Within Chania itself, strong intra-urban contrasts were also evident, as winter PM₁₀ concentrations in the city center reached 58 µg/m³, almost 2.5 times higher than the coastal background in Akrotiri, a peri-urban area of the city (Chatoutsidou et al., 2025). At the Mediterranean scale, Chania's winter levels closely matched those reported for Marseille and Venice (28–32 µg/m³) (Salameh et al., 2015). In spring, its PM_{2.5} concentrations (10–15 µg/m³) were about 40 % lower than those observed in Barcelona (20–25 µg/m³), while autumn values showed a transitional rise similar to Thessaloniki (Dimitriou and Mihalopoulos, 2024; Jaume et al., 2022). Beyond urban emissions, Saharan dust intrusions play a critical role in seasonal exceedances across the Mediterranean. In Sicily, for example, they accounted for most PM₁₀ exceedances, a pattern echoed in Chania where mineral dust contributes more than 30 % of PM mass (Chatoutsidou and Lazaridis, 2022; Cuspilici et al., 2017). In addition to particulate matters, micro-environmental conditions and other pollutants play an important role in shaping exposure risks. Lazaridis highlighted that human exposure to PM can fluctuate significantly across different urban locations (Lazaridis, 2025) supporting the present study's observation of strong intra-urban contrasts in Chania. Similarly, research on photochemical contributions to air pollution emphasizes the influence of regional and local emissions on gaseous pollutants such as NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, and SO₂ (Chatoutsidou and Lazaridis, 2024) which also exhibit trends consistent with other Mediterranean cities. Studies in Greece further confirm persistent seasonal patterns, with Athens, Thessaloniki, and Patras all recording winter peaks in PM and NO₂ due to dense traffic, industrial activities, and unfavorable meteorology (Dimitriou and Mihalopoulos, 2024).

The cluster analysis of this study further confirmed the spatial heterogeneity of air quality in Chania. The urban core consistently exhibited the poorest conditions, while coastal areas showed lower concentrations due to natural ventilation. This spatial disparity mirrors

patterns reported in other European cities such as Brussels and Milan, where dense traffic and residential activity in central districts result in systematically higher exposure than in surrounding areas (Lonati et al., 2006). These spatial disparities align with recent quality-of-life assessments in Chania, where residents in central neighborhoods reported lower satisfaction with nearby green spaces and with their overall residential environment compared to those in less dense areas. This suggests that the populations most exposed to seasonal air pollution peaks are also those with limited access to environmental amenities, compounding risks to health and well-being (Tsekeri et al., 2025). These findings support the need for localized air quality assessments, particularly in urban environments where pollution hotspots vary due to emission sources and meteorological conditions. Such findings underscore the importance of localized assessments, as also highlighted in EU-wide clustering analyses (Kuzminski and Wojtaszek, 2020), which identified regions requiring targeted interventions like the urban, sub-urban, and coastal contrasts observed in Chania.

4.1. Strengths & limitations

4.1.1. Strengths

Mobile sensors on bicycles enable high-resolution data collection, capturing air quality variations at 1-min intervals across Chania's urban routes and coastal side, amassing over 760,000 data points. This approach provides detailed spatial and temporal insights into pollution hotspots, surpassing the limitations of traditional fixed-station networks, which typically offer lower spatial resolution. For instance, it allowed robust mapping of winter peaks in the urban core (e.g., PM_{2.5} at ~30 µg/m³). Secondly, the use of ArcGIS Spatial Statistics tools, employing grouping analysis with pseudo-F-statistic plots, ensures robust identification of pollution clusters based solely on-air quality similarities, independent of spatial or administrative constraints, enhancing the accuracy of hotspot mapping. IDW interpolation generates precise heatmaps, effectively visualizing continuous pollutant distributions across Chania's urban landscape. In addition, the seasonal analysis, structured into Spring, Summer and Autumn, a comprehensive understanding of temporal pollution dynamics, grounded in established methodologies. Last, the AQI calculation, based on EPA standards, delivers a standardized, reliable metric for assessing air quality and communicating health risks to diverse stakeholders (US EPA, 2018).

4.1.2. Limitations

Despite its strengths, several methodological limitations should be considered. Firstly, the use of only two stationary monitoring stations, one on the coastal side and one in the city center, restricts spatial coverage, potentially missing critical data from industrial zones or restricted areas. Similarly, bicycle-mounted sensors are limited to cycling paths, excluding significant pollution sources in non-cycled areas such as industrial or pedestrian zones, which may underestimate overall PM. Secondly, seasonal data imbalances may compromise the robustness of clustering results, particularly for summer, potentially skewing seasonal comparisons of pollution patterns and introducing uncertainties in temporal trends. Finally, the absence of measurements for key meteorological parameters and pollutants such as wind speed and O₃, due to sensor accuracy limitations, restricts the analysis of dispersion mechanisms, particularly in summer when O₃ peaks are obvious in Mediterranean climates.

5. Conclusion

This study assessed air quality in Chania, Greece, through a hybrid monitoring approach that combined stationary sensors with mobile, bicycle-mounted devices. In total, over 760,000 data points were collected across the city, which allowed the mapping of air pollution patterns and thus overcame the spatial limitations of conventional fixed-station networks. The analysis showed that there were clear seasonal

and spatial contrasts: winter peaks in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations were largely driven by heating emissions and reduced atmospheric dispersion, whereas lower summer levels were supported by sea-breeze circulation. Moreover, intra-urban differences were observed, with the city center consistently more polluted than coastal areas. In addition, weekday concentrations were generally higher than weekend levels, although this pattern was less pronounced during the summer tourist season. To further support these findings, cluster analysis confirmed the urban core as the primary hotspot, aligning with patterns observed in other Mediterranean cities. Overall, the study demonstrates the value of integrating mobile sensing technologies into air quality monitoring frameworks. While the analysis focused on Chania, the methodology is scalable and adaptable to other mid-sized Mediterranean cities facing similar urban challenges.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Elisavet Tsekeri: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.
Aikaterini Lilli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.
Mihalis Lazaridis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis.
Dionysia Kolokotsa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Disclosure instructions

Statement: During the preparation of this work the authors used the AI tool, ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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